

“A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF *CHANDRA AVALEHA* AND *TAGARADI KWATH GHANA VATI* WITH *ELADI GUTIKA* IN TOBACCO CHEWING WITHDRAWAL: - A RANDOMIZED CLINICAL TRIAL”

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Tobacco is one of the most widely abused substances all over the world. The use of tobacco globally is mostly seen to be prevalent in low and middle-income countries. As per the Global Adult Tobacco Survey India, the percentage of tobacco use in India accounts for about 29%. Among the products of tobacco abuse, the use of smokeless tobacco like *khaini*, *gutkha*, betel quid with tobacco, and *Zarda*, etc. are the mostly used ones. As per the latest estimates by WHO, the use of tobacco in various forms will be responsible for about 13.3% of all deaths in India. **Material and methods:** Three drugs have been selected for this study viz: *Chandravaleha*, *Tagaradi Kwath Ghan vati* & *Eladi Gutika*. Accordingly 40 patients full filling the inclusion criteria were selected from the OPD of NIA, Jaipur were selected and divided into two groups (A & B) for a treatment period of 30 days with follow up for 15 days. In group A

Chandra Avaleha along with *Eladi Gutika* was given and in group B *Tagaradi Kwath Ghana*. The severity of the patients were assessed using FTND (ST) scale and Nicotine withdrawal scale both before and after treatment. Laboratory parameters like CBC, ESR and lipid profile were also assessed both before and after treatment. **Results:** The results were evaluated by

means of statistical tools both within and between the groups. On analysis both the drugs were found to be effective. However the effectiveness was seen more in Group B than Group A **Conclusion:** After the study it can be concluded that three Ayurvedic formulations used for the trail has been found effective in controlling the withdrawal symptoms of tobacco addiction.

INTRODUCTION

Tobacco addiction has emerged as one of the biggest health challenges plaguing the human population. Tobacco use in various forms may be found all across the world in both developed and developing countries. It is not only a leading cause of death, but it also causes significant economic damage. It is one of the primary cause of the majority of non-communicable diseases that humanity faces. Tobacco use in any form affects all of the body's systems, eventually leading to serious health complications such as lung cancer, bronchitis, emphysema, leukemia, heart disease, stroke, diabetes, reproductive disorders, miscarriage and pregnancy complications, respiratory infections, osteoporosis, and peptic ulcer disease.^[1] Tobacco usage is common and practiced in a number of ways in India today. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the most popular tobacco habits in India include chewing tobacco (19%), cigar cheroots (9%), hookah (9%), bidis (34%), cigarettes (31%), and snuff (2%). According to the Cancer Patients Aid Association of India, the predominance was determined to be cigarettes (20%), bidis (40%), and the remaining 40% swallowed as chewing tobacco, pan masala, snuff, gutkha, masher and tobacco toothpaste.^[2] The principle alkaloid present in tobacco is Nicotine. It is the main component responsible for cause of addiction. Nicotine is an alkaloid with addictive properties similar to cocaine, morphine, heroin, and alcohol. Nicotine has a wide range of effects in the body. It improves mood by providing a sense of well-being, reduces minor depression, decreases hunger, raises blood pressure by 5 to 10 mm hg, and raises heart rate by 10 to 20 beats per minute.^[3] However the method and dosage rate have a considerable impact on the duration of nicotine retention in the brain and other body organs, as well as the pharmacological effects that ensue. As per the DSM 5 criteria mentioned for smokeless tobacco whenever nicotine consumption ceases, withdrawal symptoms like Craving/Desire, Constipation, Restlessness/Impatience, Increase Appetite, Depression/Sadness/Tearfulness/Moodiness, Tension Bizarre/Vivid/Dreams, Frustration, Psychological Need for Tobacco, Anger, Difficulty Falling A Sleep, Difficulty remaining asleep, Irritability, Pimples, Headache, Anxiety, Difficulty in Concentration and

Mouth Sores.^[4] The above nicotine addiction symptoms appear 2 to 3 hours after the last use of tobacco products. The symptoms usually peak about 2 to 3 days after quitting.

Ayurveda hasn't described regarding tobacco addiction. However, descriptions of terms such as *Vyasana* (addiction), *Mada* (excitement), *Madatyaya* (Alcoholism), *Panatyaya* (acute alcoholism), *Vishonmada*, *Okasatyma* (habituation developed by practice), and so on can be found in some Ayurvedic classics and the symptoms arising due to the above are somewhat similar to the withdrawal symptoms of tobacco addiction.^[5] As per Ayurveda tobacco is a *Sthavara Vanaspatic Patra Visha* (immobile poison of plant origin) and regular consumption causes aggravation of *Vata* and *Pitta dosha*. So, considering the above the three Ayurvedic formulations namely *Chandra Avaleha*, *Tagaradi Kwath Ghan Vati* and *Eladi Gutika* possessing *Vata Pitta samaka* property have been selected for the present study. Thus keeping in mind the potential effects of the trial medications, they were chosen to assess their efficacy in the management of tobacco chewing withdrawal.

METHODOLOGY

AIM AND OBJECTIVE: The aim of the study was to compare the clinical efficacy of *Chandraavleha* and *Tagaradi Kwath Ghana vati* along with *Eladi Gutika* in tobacco chewing withdrawal.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Design: This was an open-label randomized comparative clinical study, prospective type. The method of generating sequence was computer generated. A computer program that generates random sequences was used to generate the random allocation sequence. Patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria were selected and divided into two groups each comprising of 20 patients. Prior consent was taken from all the patients before enrolling into the trial. To ensure that the therapies had an unbiased influence, patients were instructed to discontinue any other tobacco withdrawal medication they were taking.

Inclusion criteria: The inclusion criteria were as follows:

- Patients above the age group of 18,
- Diagnosed patient having the habit of tobacco chewing addiction or other similar products e.g *khaini*, *zarda*, *pan masala* or *gutka*.
- Patients presenting with withdrawal symptoms like craving for nicotine, anxiety, depression, restlessness etc.

- Patient willing to give consent for clinical trial, patients having history of tobacco chewing Addiction for more than 1 year up to 30 years.

Exclusion criteria: The exclusion criteria were as follows:

- Tobacco addicted patient suffering from any types of cancer
- Patients undergoing Chemotherapy and radiotherapy.
- Tobacco addicted patients who are suffering from major psychiatric disorders.
- Tobacco addicted patients suffering from major systemic illness like myocardial infarction, ischemic heart disease, pulmonary tuberculosis etc.
- Patients suffering from Diabetes Mellitus.

Sample size: The sample size for the trial was 40. Total 45 patients were registered but in between the trial 5 patients discontinued the medicines i.e. 5 drop out.

Groups: The total 40 enrolled patients were randomly divided into two groups, Group A and Group B, 20 in each group.

Drugs: Three drugs were selected for the trial. The 1st drug was *Chandra Avaleha*.^[6] It has been mentioned in *Rasatantra Sara* and *Siddha Prayoga Sangraha* in *Unmada* and *Apasmara Chikitsa Adhyaya*. It consisted of 19 ingredients (*Satavari, Vidarikanda, Saankhapusi, Sukshma Ela, Twaka, Tejpatra, Nagkeshar, Draksha, Sweta Chandan, Padma, Krishna Anata Mula, Musta, Padamaka, Usira, Amlaki, Jatamamsi, Lavang, Banchlochan* and *Sarpagandha*). The 2nd drug selected for the trial was *Tagaradi Kwath Ghan Vati*.^[7] It consisted of 12 ingredients (*Tagara, Ashwagandha, Parpat, Shankpushpi, Jyotishmati, Devadaru, Tikta, Brahmi, Nagaramotha, Aaragwadh, Haritaki* and *Draksha*). The drug has been mentioned in *Jwara chikitsa adhyaya Pralapak chikitsa*. The 3rd drug which has been common in both the groups was *Eladi Gutika*.^[8] It has been mentioned in *Rasatantrasara & Siddha Prayoga sangraha* in the context of *Kshata Kshina Adhyaya*. It consisted of 8 ingredients (*Sukshma Ela, Tejpatra, Twaka, Choti Pippali, Misri, Yastimadhu, Chuwara* and *Draksha*).

Posology: In group A the drug given was *Chandra Avaleha* and *Eladi Gutika*. The drug *Chandra Avleha* was given in a dose of 10 gm twice daily and *Anupana* advised after the drug was milk. *Eladi gutika* (250 mg) was given to be chewed 6 times daily. In group B the drug given was *Tagaradi Kwath Ghan Vati* (250 mg) and *Eladi Gutika*. The dose of *Tagaradi*

Kwath Ghan Vati was 500 mg twice daily. The *Anupana* was luke warm water. The dose of *Eladi Gutika* was same as that of Group A. The whole duration of the therapy was 30 days and follow up for 15 days.

Ethical approval: The research plan was presented before the ethical committee and the required approval was obtained vide reference No. IEC/ACA/2021/02-20. The CTRI registration for the trial was obtained on 14th July 2022 vide No. CTRI/2022/06/043253

Criteria for assessment: The following subjective and Objective parameters were assessed on the 1st and 30th day of the trial. The diagnostic tool used in the study was Fagerstrom Test for Nicotine Dependence for smokeless tobacco (FTND-ST)^[9] and Nicotine withdrawal scale which consisted of 18 symptoms (Craving/Desire, Constipation, Restlessness/Impatience, Increase Appetite, Depression/Sadness/ Tearfulness/Moodiness, Tension Bizarre/Vivid/Dreams, Frustration, Psychological Need for Tobacco, Anger, Difficulty Falling A Sleep, Difficulty remaining asleep, Irritability, Pimples, Headache, Anxiety, Difficulty in Concentration and Mouth Sores). The objective parameters like CBC, ESR and lipid profile were also assessed on the 1st and last day i.e 30th day of the trial.

Statistical analysis: The statistical evaluation was done in two steps. In the first step intra-group or within-group evaluation both before and after treatment for each group was done separately. In the second step statistical evaluation was done to compare the efficacy of the therapy in both the groups. Sigma Stat 4 was used for evaluating the data. The test used for evaluating the data has been depicted in Fig 1.

Figure 1: Depicting the test used for evaluating the parameters.

Observations: During the course of the trial following observation in context of the patients were obtained.

Out of the total 40 registered patients maximum number of patients i.e. 87.5% were male & the remaining 12.5% were females. Maximum number of registered patients i.e. 40 % was from the age group of 35-44, followed by 27.5 % patient from the age group of 25-34. Total 55 % of the registered patients belonged to the Muslim community. 60 % of the patients registered for the trial were from the urban areas. Maximum number of patients in the present study i.e. 55 % was from the lower economic class. 60% of the patients were having *Vata* and *Pitta* as their predominant *Shariraka Prakriti*. The manashik *prakriti* of the patients enrolled in the trail were *Rajashik* and *Tamashik*. 42% of the patients registered for the trial were having *Avara Samhana*. Maximum number of registered patients i.e. 57.5% of the patients had *Avara Satmya*. Maximum number of registered patients i.e. 50% of the patients had *krura kosta*. 47.5 % of the patients registered in the trial had *vishamagni* because nicotine potentiates gastric aggressive factor and attenuates defensive factors. Total 87.5 % of the patients had chronic onset and lastly it was observed that 85 % of patients took tobacco more than three to five times a day.

RESULT

Result of Fagerstorm test (FNTD-ST) in Group A: Out of the six variable mentioned in the Fagerstorm test(FNTD-ST) highly significant result was obtained in the 1st variable (How soon after you wake up do you have your first dip?), next 4 variables (How often do you intentionally swallow tobacco juice?; Which chew would you hate most to give up?; How many pouches do you use per week?; Do you chew more frequently during the first hours after walking than during the rest of the day ?) respectively showed significant result while Non-significant result was obtained in the last variable (Do you chew if you are so ill that you are in bed most of the day?). It is depicted in table no. 1.

Result of Fagerstorm test (FNTD-ST) in Group B: Out of the six variables mentioned in the trial highly significant results were obtained in 1st (How soon after you wake up do you have your first dip?) 2nd (How often do you intentionally swallow tobacco juice?) and 4th (How many pouches do you use per week?) variable, Significant result were obtained in 3rd (Which chew would you hate most to give up) and 5th variable (Do you chew more frequently during the first hours after walking than during the rest of the day?) while Non-significant

results were obtained in the 6th variable (Do you chew if you are so ill that you are in bed most of the day?). It is depicted in table no: 1.

Table No. 1: Depicting the results of intragroup (FTND – ST) score (Wilcoxon Signed rank Test).

Variable	Groups	Mean		Mean Diff.	Relief %	SD±	SE±	P	S
		BT	AT						
How soon after you wake up do you have your First dip?(0-3)	A	2.20	1.15	1.05	47.73	0.51	0.11	< 0.0001	HS
	B	2.00	0.90	1.10	55.00	0.31	0.07	< 0.0001	HS
How often do you intentionally swallow tobacco juice?(0-2)	A	1.80	1.45	0.35	19.44	0.47	0.11	0.0156	S
	B	1.80	0.75	1.05	58.33	0.22	0.05	< 0.0001	HS
Which chew would you hate most to give up (0-1)	A	0.70	0.40	0.30	42.86	0.49	0.11	0.0313	S
	B	1.10	0.70	0.40	36.36	0.50	0.11	0.0078	S
How many pouches do you use per week?(0-3)	A	2.15	1.65	0.50	23.26	0.51	0.11	0.0020	S
	B	2.20	1.55	0.65	29.55	0.49	0.11	0.0002	HS
Do you chew more frequently during the first hours after Waking than during the rest of the day ? (0-1)	A	0.80	0.50	0.30	37.50	0.47	0.11	0.0313	S
	B	0.80	0.45	0.35	43.75	0.49	0.11	0.0156	S
Do you chew if you are so ill that you are in bed Most of the day?	A	0.20	0.05	0.15	75.00	0.37	0.08	0.2500	NS
	B	0.30	0.20	0.10	33.33	0.31	0.07	0.5000	NS

Result of treatment on Group A's nicotine withdrawal scale

Out of the 18 withdrawal symptoms significant results were obtained in 13 symptoms (Craving/Desire, Constipation, Restlessness/Impatience, Increase appetite, Depression/Sadness/Tearfulness/Moodiness, Tension, Frustration, Anger, Difficulty Falling asleep, Irritability, Pimples, Difficulty in Concentration, Mouth Sores) and non- significant result were obtained in 5 withdrawal symptoms namely Bizarre/Vivid/Dreams+, Psychological Need for tobacco, Difficulty Remaining asleep, Headache, Anxiety). It is depicted in table No. 2.

Result of treatment on Group B's nicotine withdrawal scale

Out of the 18 withdrawal symptoms highly significant results were obtained in 9 symptoms (Craving/ Desire, Constipation, frustration, Psychological Need for tobacco

Restlessness/Impatience, Tension, Frustration, , Difficulty Falling asleep, and Difficulty in Concentration), significant results were obtained in 7 withdrawal symptoms (Increase Appetite, Anger, Difficulty Remaining asleep, Irritability, Pimples, Headache and Anxiety) and non-significant results were obtained only in 2 symptoms (Depression/Sadness/Tearfulness/Moodiness and Bizarre/Vivid/Dreams+). It is depicted in table No. 2.

Table No 2: Depicting the Intragroup Result in Nicotine withdrawal scale (Wilcoxon signed Rank Test).

Sr. No.	Variable	Groups	Mean		Mean Diffn.	% of Relief	SD±	SE±	P	Results
			BT	AT						
1.	Craving/ Desire	A	3.10	2.75	0.35	11.29	0.49	0.11	0.0156	S
		B	2.65	1.75	0.90	33.96	0.31	0.07	< 0.0001	HS
2.	Constipation	A	1.95	1.60	0.35	17.95	0.49	0.11	0.0156	S
		B	2.00	0.90	1.10	55.00	0.55	0.12	< 0.0001	HS
3.	Restlessness Impatience	A	1.70	1.20	0.50	29.41	0.51	0.11	0.0020	S
		B	1.75	1.10	0.65	37.14	0.49	0.11	0.0002	HS
4.	Increase Appetite	A	1.85	1.50	0.35	18.92	0.49	0.11	0.0156	S
		B	1.50	1.10	0.40	26.67	0.50	0.11	0.0078	S
5.	Depression/Sadness/ Tearfulness/Moodiness	A	0.95	0.60	0.35	36.84	0.49	0.11	0.0156	S
		B	0.80	0.55	0.25	31.25	0.44	0.10	0.0625	NS
6.	Tension	A	0.80	0.40	0.40	50.00	0.50	0.11	0.0078	S
		B	1.10	0.45	0.65	59.09	0.49	0.11	0.0002	HS
7.	Bizarre/Vivid Dreams+	A	0.65	0.40	0.25	38.46	0.55	0.65	0.1094	NS
		B	0.60	0.45	0.15	25.00	0.41	0.09	0.2500	NS
8.	Frustration	A	0.80	0.50	0.30	37.50	0.47	0.11	0.0313	S
		B	0.85	0.20	0.65	76.47	0.59	0.13	0.0005	HS
9.	Psychological Need for tobacco	A	1.80	1.60	0.20	11.11	0.41	0.09	0.1250	NS
		B	1.85	0.95	0.90	48.65	0.55	0.12	< 0.0001	HS
10.	Anger	A	1.30	0.95	0.35	26.92	0.49	0.11	0.0156	S
		B	1.10	0.75	0.35	31.82	0.49	0.11	0.0156	S
11.	Difficulty Falling asleep	A	1.75	1.30	0.45	25.71	0.51	0.11	0.0039	S
		B	1.70	1.15	0.55	32.35	0.51	0.11	0.0010	HS
12.	Difficulty Remaining asleep	A	1.00	0.80	0.20	20.00	0.44	0.10	0.1250	NS
		B	1.45	0.95	0.50	34.48	0.51	0.11	0.0020	S
13.	Irritability	A	1.25	0.85	0.40	32.00	0.50	0.11	0.0078	S
		B	1.40	1.05	0.35	25.00	0.49	0.11	0.0156	S
14.	Pimples	A	0.70	0.40	0.30	42.86	0.48	0.11	0.0313	S
		B	1.20	0.85	0.35	29.17	0.49	0.11	0.0156	S
15.	Headache	A	0.50	0.35	0.15	30.00	0.59	0.13	0.3750	NS
		B	1.40	1.10	0.30	21.43	0.47	0.11	0.0313	S
16.	Anxiety	A	0.80	0.70	0.10	12.50	0.55	0.12	0.5625	NS
		B	1.55	1.00	0.55	35.48	0.51	0.11	0.0020	S
17.	Difficulty in	A	0.50	0.20	0.30	60.00	0.47	0.11	0.0313	S

	Concentration	B	1.45	0.90	0.55	37.93	0.51	0.11	0.0010	HS
18.	Mouth Sores	A	0.75	0.45	0.30	40.00	0.47	0.11	0.0313	S
		B	0.95	0.65	0.30	31.58	0.47	0.11	0.0313	S

Result of the intergroup comparison of the effect of therapy on FTND – ST scores

During the intergroup comparison only highly significant difference was obtained in the 2nd questionnaire (How often do you intentionally swallow tobacco juice?) and the rest of the 5 questionnaire showed no significant difference. It is depicted in table No: 5.

Table No. 5: Intergroup comparison of the effect of therapy on FTND scores: (Mann Whitney Test).

Variable	Mean		SD		SE		U	P	S
	Gr-A	Gr-B	Gr-A	Gr-B	Gr-A	Gr-B			
How soon after you wake up do you have your	1.050	1.100	0.5104	0.3078	0.1141	0.06882	208	0.7589	NS
How often do you intentionally swallow tobacco juice? (0-2)	0.3500	1.050	0.4894	0.2236	0.1094	0.05000	333.50	<0.0001	HS
Which chew would you hate most to give up (0-1)	0.3000	0.4000	0.4702	0.5026	0.1051	0.1124	220	0.5233	NS
How many pouches do you use per week?(0-3)	0.5000	0.6500	0.5130	0.4894	0.1147	0.1094	170.00	0.3515	NS
Do you chew more frequently during the first hours after Walking than during the rest of the day?(0-1)	0.3000	0.3500	0.4702	0.4894	0.1051	0.1094	190.00	0.7515	NS
Do you chew if you are so ill that you are in bed most of the day?	0.1500	0.1000	0.3663	0.3078	0.08192	0.06882	190.00	0.6538	NS

Result of the intergroup comparison of the effect of therapy on Nicotine withdrawal scale

In case of intergroup comparison in Nicotine withdrawal scale highly significant difference in efficacy of the drugs in Group A and Group B was seen in the 3 withdrawal symptoms like Craving, constipation and psychological need for tobacco, significant

difference in efficacy of the drugs was seen in anxiety while non-significant difference in efficacy of the drugs were seen in rest of the withdrawal symptoms like Restlessness / Impatience, Increase Appetite, Depression / Sadness / Tearfulness/Moodiness, Tension, Bizarre / Vivid Dreams +, Frustration, Anger, Difficulty Falling Asleep, Difficulty Remaining asleep, Irritability, Pimples, Headache, Difficulty in concentration and Mouth Sores.

Table no. 6: Effects of therapy on the Nicotine Withdrawal Scale compared across both groups. (Mann Whitney Test).

Sr. no	Variable	Mean		SD		SE		U	P	S
		Gr-A	Gr-B	Gr-A	Gr-B	Gr-A	Gr-B			
1.	Craving /Desire	0.350	0.9000	0.4894	0.3078	0.1094	0.06882	310.00	0.0004	HS
2.	Constipation	0.350	1.100	0.4894	0.5525	0.1094	0.1235	324.00	0.0002	HS
3.	Restlessness Impatience	0.500	0.6500	0.5130	0.4894	0.1147	0.1094	230.00	0.3515	NS
4.	Increase Appetite	0.350	0.4000	0.4894	0.5026	0.1094	0.1124	210.00	0.7593	NS
5.	Depression/Sadness/Tearfulness /Moodiness	0.350	0.2500	0.4894	0.4443	0.1094	0.09934	220.00	0.5065	NS
6.	Tension	0.400	0.6500	0.5026	0.4894	0.1124	0.1094	250.00	0.1218	NS
7.	Bizarre/Vivid/Dreams+	0.250	0.1500	0.5501	0.3663	0.1230	0.08192	221.50	0.4507	NS
8.	Frustration	0.300	0.6500	0.4702	0.5871	0.1051	0.1313	263.00	0.0521	NS
9.	Psychological Need For Tobacco	0.200	0.9000	0.4104	0.5525	0.09177	0.1235	324.00	0.0002	HS
10.	Anger	0.350	0.3500	0.4894	0.4894	0.1094	0.1094	200.00	0.9869	NS
11.	Difficulty Falling Asleep	0.450	0.5500	0.5104	0.5104	0.1141	0.1141	220.00	0.5426	NS
12.	Difficulty Remaining asleep	0.200	0.5000	0.4104	0.5130	0.09177	0.1147	260.00	0.0515	NS
13.	Irritability	0.400	0.3500	0.5026	0.4894	0.1124	0.1094	210.00	0.7593	NS
14.	Pimples	0.300	0.3500	0.4702	0.4894	0.1051	0.1094	210.00	0.7515	NS
15.	Headache	0.150	0.3000	0.5871	0.4702	0.1313	0.1051	224.00	0.4381	NS
16.	Anxiety	0.100	0.5500	0.5525	0.6048	0.1235	0.1352	272.00	0.0256	S
17.	Difficulty in concentration	0.300	0.5500	0.4702	0.5104	0.1051	0.1141	250.00	0.1180	NS
18.	Mouth Sores	0.300	0.3000	0.4702	0.4702	0.1051	0.1051	200.00	0.9864	NS

Result of the therapy on Objective parameters

In case of objective parameters no significant result were obtained both during intragroup and inter group Comparison.

Overall effect of the therapy

When overall effect of the therapy was analyzed it was seen that in Group B 15 patients showed mild improvement while only 7 patients showed mild improvement in Group A. 5 patients showed no improvement in Group B on the other hand 13 patients showed no improvement in Group A. It is depicted in table no 7 & figure No. 2

DISCUSSION

Discussion on mode of action of the drug

Mode of action of *Chandra avaleha*: In *Rasatantrasaara* and *Siddha Prayoga Sangraha*, the drug *Chandra Avaleha* is discussed in the context of *Unmada* and *Apasmara Chikitsa Adhyaya*. It is made up of 19 components, the majority of which consist of Madhura, Tikta Rasa Laghu Guna, and Sheet Virya properties. Because of the aforementioned qualities, it functions as *Vata Pittasamaka*, *Rasayana*, and *Medya*. Addiction, as we all know, has an adverse effect on the central nervous system. When the CNS is out of balance, the *Vata* and *Pitta doshas* become aggravated, which is the core cause of the 18 withdrawal symptoms described before, such as anxiety, insomnia, restlessness, and so on. Because the drug's constituents include Vata Pitta Samaka properties, it is particularly helpful in treating withdrawal symptoms. Again, most of the ingredients, such as Sankha Puspi and Amlaki, have Medhya and Rasayana properties, which helped the patient regain immunity and health while also creating self-confidence to overcome the withdrawal effect caused by addiction.

Furthermore, Ela contains the Vishaghna characteristic, which mitigates the effect of tobacco, which is a vegetative cardiac toxin. It is also beneficial in treating tobacco-related Mukharoga, such as leukoplakia, mouth ulcers, mouth cancer, and other oral disorders. Because the bulk of the components include anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antibacterial, sedative, and hepatoprotective actions. It was extremely beneficial in gastrointestinal, cardiovascular, and neurological problems.

Mode of action of *Tagaradi Kwath Ghan Vati*: *Tagaradi kwath ghan vati* has been taken from *Yogratnakar Jwara Pralapak chikitsa adhyaya*. It is made up of 12 components. *Medhya* and *Vishaghna* qualities are found in components such as *Tagar*, *Sankhpushpi*, and

Brahmi. Because tobacco is a vegetative cardiac toxin, it counteracted its effect. Because of its *Medhya* (brain tonic) effect, it also lowers molecular changes at the neurotransmitter level in the brain. Addiction is a brain disorder that causes chemical changes at the neurotransmitter level, such as dopamine and acetylcholine. As the ingredients of *Tagaradi Kwath Ghan Vati* has *Medhya, Mashtishka shamaka, Nadi balya, Nidrajanana* property It probably reduced the chemical changes at the neurotransmitter level in the brain. So the patients were able to get relief from the symptoms. Moreover the majority of the ingredients of the drug have *Tikta Rasa* and *Sheeta Virya* qualities, so it was able to alleviate the clinical manifestations (withdrawal symptoms) like insomnia, anxiety & agitation, depression, anger, and so on.

Mode of action of *Eladi Gutika*: *Eladi Gutika* which was used as a common drug in both the groups has been mentioned in *Rasatantrasaara* and *Siddha Prayoga Sangraha* in the context of *Uraah Kshat* diseases. It consist of 8 ingredients.

The reason for choosing the medicine is that tobacco addiction has a significant impact on human immunity. As a result of decreased immunity, the human body becomes susceptible to a variety of diseases. As tobacco chewing is responsible for bad oral hygiene, the ingredients like *Sukshma Ela, Tejpatra* present in *Eladi Gutika* helped in removing the foul odour which not only contributed to the patients general wellbeing but also psychologically boosted their self-confidence. Again Nicotine has a half life of 2 hrs. in the human body. Once this time period is over further craving for nicotine occurs. So *Eladi Gutika* chewed by the patient 6 times per day had a psychological impact in controlling the Craving. Lastly as per the theory “**chew on this: the need to engage your mouth and hands after quitting**” postulated by the quitters circle staff on 10th of March 2015, if a tobacco addicted person is kept engaged by putting a medicated *gutika* in the mouth at the time of craving it will not only be beneficial for the health but will also be able to produce a psychologically feel good effect. With this intent *Eladi gutika* has been given to chew 6 times per day in both the groups. As the patients were engaged in chewing, it created a psychological effect and thus improvements in withdrawal symptoms were seen.

CONCLUSION

Although no description regarding the treatment of Tobacco chewing addiction and withdrawal can be in Ayurvedic classics but drugs like *Chandra avaleha, & Tagaradi Kwath Ghan Vati* as indicated in *Manashik rogas* like *Unmada, Apasmara & pralapa*

respectively is found to be effective in treating tobacco chewing addiction and withdrawal symptoms as the symptoms of the mentioned diseases are similar to the withdrawal symptoms of tobacco addiction. Moreover *Eladi gutika* given for chewing in both groups provided a feel-good psychological effect and at the same time prevented him from putting further tobacco in the mouth. Overall after the above study it can be concluded that the above drugs used for the trial had some impact on the neurotransmitter and reward pathway system or as per Ayurveda controlling the aggravated *Vata* and *pitta* dosha, which definitely lead to control of tobacco chewing withdrawal symptoms.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No conflict of interest.

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